

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R6.4 Data set and report with results of well integrity logging

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1 INTRODUCTION

Risk analysis is very important part of all CO₂ storage projects. In frame of CO₂-SPICER project, the work package (WP) 6 “Risk Analysis” is focused, besides other things, on hazard identification, leakage potential from wellbores including. To obtain reliable data and information on current status of wells penetrating our storage site Zar-3, a well log survey focused on well integrity status was planned in one of the site wells (see Project content & Detailed Description of Work Packages, WP6, Task 6.1, Sub-task6.1.1). The logging methods such a Cement Bond Logs (CBL) and Acoustic Televiewer (ATV) can provide up-to-date information on the status of the well, casing and cement after up to 20 years of exposure to the aggressive reservoir environment with presence of brine, natural gas and crude oil but also certain amounts of CO₂ and H₂S.

In accordance with Project content, the well integrity logging measurement was performed by sub-contractor - we have chosen the Czech company Karotáž a cementace (KaC), the only one in the Czech Republic with adequate equipment and experience. The project partner MND has selected well ZA7 (Žarošice 7) for well integrity logging (just after workover) and provided on site assistance to the sub-contractor.

For well integrity logging, Cement Bond Logging and Acoustic Televiewer were selected as main methods; gamma ray log and casing collar locator were used as complementary logging methods. Density of fluid (mud) inside of the borehole was 1.01 kg/dm³.

The measurement of well integrity logging was performed on November 12, 2023.

2 CEMENT BOND LOGGING

The Cement Bond Logging (CBL) tools have become the standard method of evaluating cement jobs. They indicate how good the cement bond is. A CBL documents an evaluation of the integrity of cement job performed on a well. It is basically a sonic tool which is run on wireline. Similar to a ringing bell, when no cement is bonded to the casing, pipe is free to vibrate (loud sound). When the casing is bonded to hard cement, casing vibrations are attenuated proportionally to bonded surface.

2.1 CBL task and logging interval

The objective of measurement was to evaluate cementation behind 7" production casing and to evaluate the well integrity. Logging interval of CBL was 523.0 - 1905.9 m (measured depth).

2.2 CBL interpretation

The quality of measured logs is good. The CBL tool started measuring at the depth of 523 m due to the loss of fluid (mud) in borehole. This logging can be done in a well with fluid, not in a dry well). Only gamma ray (GR) and casing collar locator (CCL), both complementary logging methods, were measured from the top (wellhead). The logs were depth shifted to open-hole data.

CBL was evaluated and interpreted qualitatively. The graphic processing of CBL is shown in Annex 1. Partially missing cement is very probably replaced by caprocks. The head of cement behind the 7" production casing is at the depth of 1373 m.

Depth interval	CBL evaluation
0 - 1373 m	without cement, free pipe
1373 - 1460 m	most probably mud bad bond for casing and formation
1460 - 1866 m	very good bond for casing and formation
1866 - 1905.9 m	very good bond, partially intermediate bond for casing and formation

3 ACOUSTIC TELEVIEWER

Borehole imaging tool “Acoustic Televierer (ATV)” is an advanced probe, which records 3D image of the borehole wall and is used to obtain oriented images of bore hole and provides substantial information regarding lithology, structural information, and detection of fractures and casing of the borehole

The acoustic probe generates an image of the borehole wall by transmitting ultrasonic pulses from a fixed transducer with rotating mirror and recording the amplitude and travel time of the signals reflected at the interface between borehole fluid and the formation (borehole wall). A harder borehole surface translates to higher amplitude recorded by the tool, whereas softer surfaces, fractures, and void spaces are recorded at a lower relative amplitude. In boreholes with casing, the recorded amplitude can show a condition of casing (corrosion, damages).

Acoustic televierers work best in boreholes that are smooth, circular, and have a high acoustic impedance contrast between the borehole fluid and borehole wall or casing. In such condition, the acoustic televierer QL-43 (used for this measurement) can detected also the thickness of casing strings.

3.1 ATV task and logging interval

The objective of the measurement was to evaluate production casing integrity. Logging interval of ATV was 524.0 - 1905.9 m (measured depth).

3.2 ATV interpretation

The inner surface of the casing was mostly satisfactory for the measurements carried out, with the exception of the interval 1871 - 1905.9 m. In this interval, the measurement was greatly affected by sediments on the inside of the casing. For that reason, the measured inner diameters of the casing (Cal-min, Cal-max, Cal-av) are not relevant in this interval. It seems that the workover on the well ZA7 was not fully successful...

The ATV measurement at the depth of 524 m due to the loss of fluid (mud) in borehole. This logging, similarly to CBL, can be done in a well with fluid, not in a dry well. Results of ATV logging show casing thickness 9.19 mm with allowed tolerance. No perforation as well as no significant casing thickness reduction was detected. Also the ovality of casing is mostly on good level. ATV measurement detects slight impact of corrosion on the production casing.

ATV measurement was depth correlated with CBL, gamma ray log (GR) and casing collar locator (CCL). The graphic processing of ATV is shown in Annex 2.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Results of well integrity logging in well ZA7 demonstrate that after 20 year (ZA7 was drilled in 2003) of exposure to the aggressive reservoir environment with presence of brine, natural gas and crude oil but also certain amounts of CO₂ and H₂S is still in good condition.

CO₂ injection will represent more aggressive environment in Zar-3 storage site. In this case, the well integrity logging has to be planned and realized relatively often; currently no legislative regulation defines a frequency of such measurement.

Annexes

Annex 1: CBL + GR + CCL graphic processing

Annex 2: ATV graphic processing

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More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz

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ANNEX 1

Graphic processing of Gamma Ray logging (GR), the first curve from left for the depth interval 0 - 1906 m, Casing Collar Locator (CCL), the second curve from left for the depth interval 0 - 1906 m and Cement Bond Logging (CBL), all other curves for the depth interval 523 - 1906 m.

BONDIX	3FT TRAVEL TIME	3FT AMPLITUDE	0	AMPAVG	200	WWF3FT	0	WWF3FT	1000
1	0 150 (usec) 550	0 (mV) 100	0	AMPMAX	200	200 (usec) 1200			
	-3 CCL 1	3FT AMPx5	0	AMPMIN	200	TT3FT			
	0 GR (GAPI) 200	0 (mV) 20				200 (usec) 1200			
		-100 ATT3 (db/m) 0							

125

150

175

200

225

250

275

300

325

350

375

400

550

575

600

625

650

675

700

725

750

775

800

825

850

875

900

925

950

975

1000

1025

1050

1075

1100

1250
1275
1300
1325
1350
1375

BONDIX	3FT TRAVEL TIME	3FT AMPLITUDE	0	AMPAVG	200	WVF3FT	0	WVF3FT	1000
1	0 150 (usec) 550	0 (mV) 100	0	AMPMAX	200	200 (usec) 1200			
	-3 CCL 1	3FT AMPx5	0	AMPMIN	200	TT3FT			
	0 GR (GAPI) 200	0 (mV) 20				200 (usec) 1200			
		-100 ATT3 (db/m) 0							

ANNEX 2

Graphic processing of Acoustic Televiewer (ATV) for the depth interval 523 - 1906 m.

